

A Case Study of Amul: Implementation of Extension Strategy to Repositioning Brand During Covid-19 Period

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Abstract: During lockdown and consequent pandemic, many organizations reduced their production, and few shut their operations. Some organizations continued their regular production. Apart from Pharma, very few organizations raised their production and raised their sales. Amul, a dairy products company is the one which in addition to raising production and sales, established an emotional and social connection with their clients. The advantage of essential commodity category and milk production aided its success during the pandemic. In this paper, the marketing strategy of Amul is review as backbone of their success being the advertising strategy.

Keywords: advertising, Amul, business during pandemic, social media advertising.

1 INTRODUCTION

Amul, a leading dairy fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) brand has continued to produce potent products. Amul has continued with its inventive marketing to create positioning stay during lockdown period. When the public authorities announced the nationwide lockdown influenced by March 25th, 2020, Amul conveyed to consumers through their products that they should "keep well" and "not hungry." 'We were able to beat the effect on request thanks to a notable development in the sales of our customers'.

To let customers, use compass to prepare café-style foods at home, the idea of elevating aims to educate and enlighten them. Extremely improved media spend agreements for client's dairy brand. Amul continued to wow customers with their creative diamonds, which is what it does best. The company promptly decided to more kind proportional advertisement budget double to create positive environment in the nation with heart touching advertising [1][2].

2 HISTORY

Anand Milk Union Limited, usually called as Amul is a well-known dairy brand in India having headquarters at Anand, Gujarat established in 1946. It is a cooperative brand administered by the Gujarat Co-operative Milk Marketing Federation Ltd. (GCMMF), a cooperative firm owned by 3.6 million Gujarati milk producers and the heads of 13 District Milk Unions, which are distributed throughout 13,000 villages in Gujarat. India's White Revolution, sparked by Amul, resulted to the nation becoming world's leading producer of milk and milk-related products. Kaira Union created the "Amul" brand with the intention of marketing its variety of products. The name "Amul" was suggested by Dr. Maganbhai Patel, who served as Agriculture College's founding president, and was carried out with the guidance of Tribhuvandas Kishibhai Patel. The white revolution in India received a substantial support from the Amul Foundation [3][4].

3 ADAPTATION OF PROMOTIONAL STRATEGY DURING PENDING

During the phase of pandemic, advertisers drastically cut on their advertising spend, dairy brand Amul remained spend huge amount to impressed consumers with its innovative advertising. The company decided to double its advertising expenses after grasping the opportunity. Interestingly, families seemed to have preferred a trustworthy brand over loose milk, as demand for Amul's liquid bottled milk has climbed by 5-7% that since pre-Covid period. Despite recent closure of hotels and restaurants, interest for its cheese and paneer products has risen by a minimum of 30%, and sales of butter and ghee have climbed by 10% to 20%. The company gains praise from experts for keeping on with its delightful advertising despite the storms. Amul maintained its authenticity by maintaining a joyful, likeable atmosphere. Never went crazy with Covid or tall immunity claims. Furthermore, never ceased to produce, distribute, sell, or advertise. Important marketing lesson to be learned [5].

TAM AdEx statistics show that Amul's ad volumes climbed triple (316%) during the months of April and May compared to the same period previous year. Amul's ad volume has increased by about 21% from April to May. In addition to the channel's well-liked broadcasts of the "Ramayana" and "Mahabharat" every Sunday, the brand also re-released vintage commercials. According to N Chandramouli, CEO of TRA, committed, Amul started to dominate the TV media in advertising as soon as the lockdown was revealed. Amul is one of the few firms that can really claims to have influenced the lives of the overwhelming majority of Indians. One of India's most effective marketing firms is Amul. It made sense for Amul, as R S Sodhi explained, because families were devouring information like never before during the lockdown.

3.1 The Topicality Quotient

Amul was commended for employing its proactive approach and aggressive implementation successfully, as per branding strategist Jagdeep Kapoor and founder and CEO of Samsika. Amul "The Taste of India" has taken the decision to utilize time since the lockdown commenced. It skyrocketed in vibrant awareness and powerful brand recall using advertising on Doordarshan in specialist of maximum views TV serials like "Ramayan" and "Shri Krishna" to display the entire range of Amul products [6].

According to Kapoor, the brand's appeal was boosted by bringing in memories through adorable old advertisements. "New advertising were produced rapidly and played on multiple channels, including news stations, which are currently closely watched. Amul became a bigger family member as a result of a personalized connection, enhancing consumer loyalty to the brand. According to Kapoor, the family providing Amul products with love and an emphasis on daughters and moms, together with outstanding brand distribution and availability. When domestic flight started then again contemporary campaign for Amul on May 25 said, "AB BOARDING PAAS HAI." After already being banned for two months due to the country's coronavirus pandemic, national air travel restarted on May 25 with a limited number of departures. Another Amul creation, however, "MBBS: MAKHAN BOLE BAHUT SHUKRIYA," expressing gratitude for the medical practitioners who have led the fight against COVID. The company's managers of its advertising creative are in touch with mood of the nation and use it as a necessary element of their advertising. Therefore, it rarely disappoints. Amul tripled advertising budgets during that period [7].

3.2 Creative Positioning

On February 4, Amul's official Twitter account posted the comic work "**Wuhan Se Yahaan Le Aaye**," that has since received over 1,000 likes. Before propagating around the world, the virus was firstly discovered in Wuhan city. Amul's brand picture girl can be seen departing an Air India plane with a group of strangers all of whom are wearing masks, garnering the imaginative moniker "homecoming snack of India." However, views amongst social media users about just the creative's inspirations differed. Amul's official Twitter account shared the comic creation with the caption "Better saaf than sorry," shown in Fig. 1 and it has received about 1,000 likes in few hours [8].

Fig. 1. Amul "Better saaf than sorry" Tweet [9]

Social media has been flooded with responses since the post gained traction. "Only precautions can help, please share maximum knowledge," a user commented. Someone else said, "Very relevant and unique!" "Face Corona...Mat Darona," read a post. 'As usual, spot on!' a user exclaimed. Here are a few original topicals Amul published when the lockdown remained in place [10] as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Amul "Khaali haath nahin" Tweet [9]

Amul's topical titled "Aatmakhanirbhar," which reiterated the Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan of the Narendra Modi emphasised the importance of independent India to combat the issue as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Amul “Aatmakhanirbhar” Tweet [9]

The Amul advertisement read, "MBBS: Makhan Bole Bahut Shukriya," expressing gratitude to the medical professionals who have been leading the charge against the deadly coronavirus as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Amul “MBBS” Tweet [9]

Amul created an advertising in which it shows colour of areas with yellow zones as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Amul “Yellow Zone” Tweet [9]

Following the success of Ramayan, which was replayed on Doordarshan, they released the topical as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Amul “Ramayan” Tweet [9]

This, in turn, made videoconferencing apps an instant hit with millions across India accessing it. In addition to a sales pitch, marketing strategy is like producing long-term wealth. The consumer is a family member to us, therefore communication with them via advertising is more important. We should therefore talk more rather than less than if a family member is upset. Amul carried out his purpose in fully. In the months of April and May 2020, as according to TAM Adex data,

- When compared to same period last year, Amul's advertainment spending reached to 316 percent.
- Comparatively to other summer advertising, such as bottled juice companies, Amul had a 51% market share. "Ramayan" and "Mahabharat" returned on Doordarshan,
- "You merely need to organize the Amul hoardings in chronological order if you wish to record the major occasions that occurred during the three months of the lockdown. The client, who is unconcerned with media planning, was moved by some of their incredibly effective advertising that they generated in the previous two to three months,
- The amount of milk we purchased increased by 17%, while sales of milk, butter, paneer, and other dairy products increased by 30% to 40%.

3.3 Sales during Pandemic Period

Despite COVID-19 epidemic, the company's total revenue, which includes sales of dairy products, increased by 2% to 39,200 crores. A 17% increase in income to 38,550 crore was reported by GCMMF for the 2019–20 fiscal year. The turnover of its branded consumer goods, such as fresh milk, cheese, curd, buttermilk, and paneer, however, climbed by 8.5–9 percent. The nationwide lockdown in the summer was the main reason why ice cream sales last fiscal year were down 35%. Products like skim milk powder (SMP) were affected in the commodity market. A daily 150 lakh litres of milk are sold by the cooperative. Approximate contributions from Gujarat are 60 lakh litres, Delhi-NCR is 35 lakh litres, and Maharashtra is 20 lakh litres. In addition, Kolkata, Uttar Pradesh, and Punjab sell milk through it. GCMMF can process 360 lakh litres of liquid per day at its installed capacity.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a review of Amul advertising and marketing strategies are reviewed. During COVID pandemic, the company has seen a great success in terms of production and sales. In addition to company's revenue, the emotional connection between the clients and the organization was strengthened. This was mainly because of its simple and yet effective media connection through television, newspaper and social platform advertising. The daily and/or event-wise tweets has attracted many clients and public. In this paper, key tweets, sales data, and revenue details are presented.

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